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Development of Progressive Failure Analysis Method for Composite Laminates Containing Openings with Digital Image Correlation

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1. Introduction

Fibers in a composite generally alternate direction.
Illustration by Steve Karp

FIGURE 7.33

Idealized load–strain curve for uniaxially loaded laminate showing multiple sequential ply failures leading up to ultimate laminate failure.

- Composite laminates are widely used in mechanical and aerospace industries
- Composite laminate does not lead directly to fracture of the whole structure even if some plies are broken.
- The progressive behavior can be implemented more accurately through FEM, enabling more efficient design.

2. objectives

- Progressive failure analysis (PFA) method was developed based on **crack band model** implemented damage variables.
- To perform the analysis, **mechanical properties and fracture energies** were obtained experimentally.
- To evaluate the developed PFA model, experimental results were compared with the computational results.
- Failure behavior of notched composite laminate was studied using the developed PFA model.

Development and evaluation of PFA model for composite laminate to design structures

3. Progressive failure analysis

➤ C_d (Damaged stiffness matrix)

$$[C_d] = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

➤ $\tilde{\sigma}$ (Effective stress), and M (Damage operator)

$$\tilde{\sigma} = M\sigma \quad [M] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{(1-d_f)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{(1-d_m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-d_m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-d_s)} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-d_s)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-d_s)} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_{11} = \frac{(E_1(1-d_f)(v_{23}v_{32}(1-d_m)^2-1))}{((1-d_m)^2((v_{12}v_{23}v_{31}+v_{13}v_{21}v_{32})(1-d_f)+v_{23}v_{32})+(v_{12}v_{21}+v_{13}v_{31})(1-d_f)(1-d_m)-1)}$$

$$C_{12} = \frac{(-E_1(1-d_m)(1-d_f)(v_{23}v_{31}(1-d_m)+v_{21}))}{((1-d_m)^2((v_{12}v_{23}v_{31}+v_{13}v_{21}v_{32})(1-d_f)+v_{23}v_{32})+(v_{12}v_{21}+v_{13}v_{31})(1-d_f)(1-d_m)-1)}$$

$$C_{13} = \frac{(-E_1(1-d_m)(1-d_f)(v_{21}v_{32}(1-d_m)+v_{31}))}{((1-d_m)^2((v_{12}v_{23}v_{31}+v_{13}v_{21}v_{32})(1-d_f)+v_{23}v_{32})+(v_{12}v_{21}+v_{13}v_{31})(1-d_f)(1-d_m)-1)}$$

$$C_{22} = \frac{(E_2(1-d_m)(v_{13}v_{31}(1-d_m)(1-d_f)-1))}{((1-d_m)^2((v_{12}v_{23}v_{31}+v_{13}v_{21}v_{32})(1-d_f)+v_{23}v_{32})+(v_{12}v_{21}+v_{13}v_{31})(1-d_f)(1-d_m)-1)}$$

$$C_{23} = \frac{(-E_2(1-d_m)^2(v_{12}v_{31}(1-d_f)+v_{32}))}{((1-d_m)^2((v_{12}v_{23}v_{31}+v_{13}v_{21}v_{32})(1-d_f)+v_{23}v_{32})+(v_{12}v_{21}+v_{13}v_{31})(1-d_f)(1-d_m)-1)}$$

$$C_{33} = \frac{(E_3(1-d_m)(v_{12}v_{21}(1-d_m)(1-d_f)-1))}{((1-d_m)^2((v_{12}v_{23}v_{31}+v_{13}v_{21}v_{32})(1-d_f)+v_{23}v_{32})+(v_{12}v_{21}+v_{13}v_{31})(1-d_f)(1-d_m)-1)}$$

$$C_{44} = G_{12}(1-d_s)$$

$$C_{55} = G_{13}(1-d_s)$$

$$C_{66} = G_{23}(1-d_s)$$

3. Progressive failure analysis

➤ Damage Initiation (Hashin failure criterion)

❖ Fiber tension failure mode : $f_{FT} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^2 + \tau_{13}^2}{S_A^2}\right) = 1$

❖ Fiber compression failure mode : $f_{FC} = -\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_c} = 1$

❖ Matrix tension failure mode : $f_{MT} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_T^2}\right) + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^2 - \tau_{13}^2}{S_A^2}\right) = 1$

❖ Matrix compression failure mode : $f_{MC} = \left[\frac{Y_c^2}{2S_T} - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_c} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}}{2S_T}\right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_T^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2 + \tau_{13}^2}{S_A^2} = 1$

- During PFA, failure initiation should be detected to apply the damage evolution model.
- Damage initiation is evaluated using the Hashin failure criterion
- Once the failure initiated, the damage variable is required to be calculated to obtain the damaged stiffness matrix.

X_T : Longitudinal tensile strength, X_c : Longitudinal compressive strength, Y_T : Transverse tensile strength,

Y_c : Transverse compressive strength, S_A : Shear strength, S_T : Transverse shear strength

3. Progressive failure analysis

➤ Damage evolution (equivalent displacement & stress calculation)

- ❖ Fiber tension failure mode ($\tilde{\sigma}_{11} \geq 0$) :

$$\delta_{eq}^{ft} = L_c \sqrt{\langle \varepsilon_{11} \rangle^2 + \gamma_{12}^2 + \gamma_{13}^2}$$

$$\sigma_{eq}^{ft} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle \langle \varepsilon_{11} \rangle + \tau_{12} \gamma_{12} + \tau_{13} \gamma_{13}}{\varepsilon_{eq}^{ft}}$$

- ❖ Fiber compression failure mode ($\tilde{\sigma}_{11} < 0$) :

$$\delta_{eq}^{fc} = L_c \langle -\varepsilon_{11} \rangle$$

$$\sigma_{eq}^{fc} = \frac{\langle -\sigma_{11} \rangle \langle -\varepsilon_{11} \rangle}{\varepsilon_{eq}^{fc}}$$

- ❖ Matrix tension failure mode ($\tilde{\sigma}_{22} \geq 0$) :

$$\delta_{eq}^{mt} = L_c \sqrt{\langle \varepsilon_{22} \rangle^2 + \langle \varepsilon_{33} \rangle^2 + \gamma_{12}^2 + \gamma_{23}^2 + \gamma_{13}^2}$$

$$\sigma_{eq}^{mt} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle \langle \varepsilon_{22} \rangle + \langle \sigma_{33} \rangle \langle \varepsilon_{33} \rangle + \tau_{12} \gamma_{12} + \tau_{23} \gamma_{23} + \tau_{13} \gamma_{13}}{\varepsilon_{eq}^{mt}}$$

- ❖ Matrix compression failure mode ($\tilde{\sigma}_{22} < 0$) :

$$\delta_{eq}^{mc} = L_c \sqrt{\langle -\varepsilon_{22} \rangle^2 + \langle -\varepsilon_{33} \rangle^2 + \gamma_{12}^2 + \gamma_{23}^2 + \gamma_{13}^2}$$

$$\sigma_{eq}^{mc} = \frac{\langle -\sigma_{22} \rangle \langle -\varepsilon_{22} \rangle + \langle -\sigma_{33} \rangle \langle -\varepsilon_{33} \rangle + \tau_{12} \gamma_{12} + \tau_{23} \gamma_{23} + \tau_{13} \gamma_{13}}{\delta_{eq}^{mc}}$$

➤ To obtain the damage variables, an **equivalent displacement** and an **equivalent stress** are required to be calculated.

3. Progressive failure analysis

➤ Damage evolution (equivalent displacement & stress calculation)

- ❖ Calculation of "equivalent displacement ($\delta_{I,eq}^0$) and equivalent stress ($\sigma_{I,eq}^0$) at the initial failure state"

$$\delta_{I,eq}^0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{f_I}} \delta_{I,eq} \quad \sigma_{I,eq}^0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{f_I}} \sigma_{I,eq}$$

($\frac{1}{\sqrt{f_I}}$: scale factor, f_I : failure criteria at each failure mode)

- ❖ Using the crack band model, the "equivalent displacement at the final failure state ($\delta_{I,eq}^f$)" can be calculated.

- ❖ Smearred crack band model

$$\epsilon^f = \frac{2G_c}{\sigma_0 L_c} \rightarrow \delta_{I,eq}^f = \frac{2G_I^c}{\sigma_{I,eq}^0}$$

3. Progressive failure analysis

➤ Damage evolution (damage variable calculation)

❖ Damage variable

$$d_I = \frac{\delta_{I,eq}^f (\delta_{I,eq} - \delta_{I,eq}^0)}{\delta_{I,eq} (\delta_{I,eq}^f - \delta_{I,eq}^0)}$$

$$(\delta_{I,eq}^0 \leq \delta_{I,eq} \leq \delta_{I,eq}^f)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d = 0 : \text{undamage status} \\ 0 < d < 1 : \text{damage propagating} \\ d = 1 : \text{complete damage status} \end{array} \right\}$$

❖ Damage variable at each failure mode

$$d_f = \begin{cases} d_{ft} & \text{if } \tilde{\sigma}_{11} \geq 0 \\ d_{fc} & \text{if } \tilde{\sigma}_{11} < 0 \end{cases}, \quad d_m = \begin{cases} d_{mt} & \text{if } (\tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \tilde{\sigma}_{33}) \geq 0 \\ d_{mc} & \text{if } (\tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \tilde{\sigma}_{33}) < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$d_s = 1 - (1 - d_{ft}) (1 - d_{fc}) (1 - d_{mt}) (1 - d_{mc})$$

- Damage variables are considered in the damaged stiffness matrix in the form of $(1-d_i)$.
- Consequently, an increase in damage variables induces a decrease in the stiffness matrix.

4. Material and experimental procedures

➤ T700/Epoxy composite material properties

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
147.7	8.52	8.52	4.59	4.59	3.95	0.3	0.3	0.5
X_t (MPa)	X_c (MPa)	Y_t (MPa)	Y_c (MPa)	S_{12} (MPa)	S_{13} (GPa)	S_{23} (GPa)	G_f (kN/m ²)	G_m (kJ/m ²)
2737.92	1600	51.32	201.08	81.0	81.0	50	180	1.71

Tensile test (ASTM D3039)

FIG. 5 Schematic of Compression Test Fixture

Compression test (ASTM D3410)

FIG. 3 V-Notched Beam Test Fixture Schematic

Shear test (ASTM D5379)

4. Material and experimental procedures

➤ Open hole tensile test

<Composite open-hole tensile specimen>

Type	Stacking sequence
TYPE 1	[0/+45/-45/90] _s
TYPE 2	[0/+45/0/-45] _s

- To compare with the results of proposed PFA model, open hole tensile tests were conducted.
- Test machine : MTS810 hydraulic test machine / Test rate : 1 mm/min

4. Material and experimental procedures

➤ Digital image correlation (DIC)

5. Results

5.1 Mesh dependency

- The crack-band-model applied PFA shows less influence of mesh dependency compared to other models. (8.5% error of the maximum load)
- This is because the elements of this model are fractured considering the same fracture energies in each failure mode.

5. Results

5.2 Load–displacement curve comparison

Type 1 : $[0/+45/-45/90]_S$

Type 2 : $[0/+45/0/-45]_S$

➤ The maximum load difference between the experiment and PFA results was only **2.3%** and **0.59%** for type-1 and type-2 specimens.

5. Results

5.3 Strain field comparison

➤ PFA strain contour

➤ DIC strain field

➤ The maximum value observed from the PFA result was **0.01873**, and that from the DIC result was **0.01804**.

5. Results

5.4 Strain value comparison

<Type 1 : [0/+45/-45/90]_S>

<Type 2 : [0/+45/0/-45]_S>

- It was compared with the measured value by strain gauges.
- The maximum error was 7.03% in all specimen cases.

5. Results

5.5 Progressive failure behavior of open hole composite laminate

(a) Shear failure damage (d_s) (b) Matrix tension failure damage (d_{mt}) (c) Fiber tension failure damage (d_{ft})

6. Conclusion

- 1) Progressive failure analysis method was developed using Hashin failure criterion and crack band model.
- 2) PFA results were compared with experimental results
- 3) The analysis results were in good agreement with the experimental ones
(L-D curve, strength, strain field trend, and strain values)
- 4) The suggested model, which allows for a good representation of behavior of notched geometry and less mesh dependence, is expected to benefit in the designing process of complex composite structures.